

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

ASYMPTOTIC FORMULAS FOR SOLVING A SECOND ORDER INTEGRO-DIFFERENTIAL OPERATOR ON THE ENTIRE AXIS

Almammadov Musa

*Professor, doctor of mathematical sciences
Azerbaijan State University of Economics (UNEC)
Baku, Azerbaijan*

Abstract

In this paper we consider in $L^2(\mathbb{R}_-^+)$, where $\mathbb{R}_-^+$ is an entire axis $[-\infty, +\infty]$, a second order integro-differential (i.d.) equation

$$Ly = y''(x) + \lambda y(x) = p(x)y'(x) + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} K(x, s, \rho)y(s)ds, \quad (0.1)$$

where $\lambda = \rho^2$, $|\operatorname{Im} \rho| < \frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$ $\rho = \rho_1 + i\rho_2$.

Let $p(x)$ be a complex valued summable function in the interval $\mathbb{R}_-^+$ and kernel of integro-differential operator (0.1) have the form:

$$K(x, s, \rho) = \begin{cases} e^{-\rho\omega_1(s-x)}P(s)K^*(x, s, \rho) & \text{as } s < x \\ e^{-\rho\omega_2(s-x)}P(s)K^*(x, s, \rho) & \text{as } s > x, \end{cases} \quad (0.2)$$

where ω_1, ω_2 are various roots of second degree from -1 while $K^*(x, s, \rho)$ is a complex valued continuous bounded function on totality of variables (x, s, ρ) , $-\infty < x, s < +\infty$, $|\operatorname{Im} \rho| < \frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$ and analytic with respect to ρ in the domain $|\operatorname{Im} \rho| < \frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$ for each fixed (x, s) , $-\infty < x, s < +\infty$.

Furthermore, let the following condition be fulfilled:

$$|P(x)| \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |K^*(s, x, \rho)| ds \right] < ce^{-2\varepsilon_0|x|}, \varepsilon_0 > 0 \quad (0.3)$$

Then

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{2\varepsilon_0|x|} |P(x)| \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |K^*(s, x, \rho)| ds \right] dx < B_1 < \infty, \quad (0.4)$$

where B_1 is independent of ρ .

Here it is proved that subject to the conditions (0.2) and $\operatorname{Im} \rho < \frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$, the integro-differential equation (0.1)

has two linearly independent solutions $y_k(x, \rho)$ analytic with respect to ρ in $\operatorname{Im} \rho < \frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$ for each fixed $x \in \mathbb{R}_-^+$ and admitting the asymptotics

$$\frac{d^j y_k(x, \rho)}{dx^j} = e^{\rho\omega_k x} \left[(\rho\omega_k)^j + o(e^{2\varepsilon_0 x}) \right], \quad j = 0, 1, k = 1, 2 \quad \text{as } x \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Now, let the following condition be fulfilled:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |p(x)| \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |K^*(s, x, \rho)| ds \right] dx < B < \infty, \quad (0.5)$$

where B is independent of ρ .

Then it is proved that subject to the condition (0.5) and $|\rho| \geq r > 0, \text{Im } \rho > 0$, where $r > B$, the integro-differential equation (0.1) in the halfplane $\text{Im } \rho > 0$ has two linearly independent solutions $y_k(x, \rho), k = 1, 2$ analytic in this domain with respect to ρ for each fixed $x \in R_-^+$ and admitting the asymptotics

$$\frac{d^j y_k(x, \rho)}{dx^j} = e^{\rho \omega_k x} [(\rho \omega_k)^j + O(1)], \quad j = 0, 1, k = 1, 2$$

as $|x| \rightarrow \infty$.

Keywords: integro-differential, operator, complex-valued, equation, theorem, solution, condition, linear, kernel, interval, asymptotic, entire axis, formula, of second order, bounded, analytic, variables, fixed.

Introduction. We now consider the fundamental solution of the integro-differential equation

$$Ly = \lambda y \quad (1.1)$$

We rewrite it in the form:

$$y''(x) + \rho^2 y(x) = p(x) y'(x) + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} K(x, s, \rho) y'(s) ds. \quad (1.2)$$

Assume $\sqrt{\lambda} = \rho = \rho_1 + \omega_1 \rho_2, |\text{Im } \rho| < \frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$.

Applying the method of variation of arbitrary constants to the equation (1.2), we obtain:

$$y(x, \rho) = \sum_{i=1}^2 c_i e^{\rho \omega_i x} + \frac{\omega_1}{2\rho} \int_x^{\infty} [e^{\rho \omega_1(x-\tau)} - e^{\rho \omega_2(x-\tau)}] \times \left[p(\tau) y'(\tau, \rho) + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} K(\tau, s, \rho) y'(s, \rho) ds \right] d\tau \quad (1.3).$$

Theorem 1.1. Let the condition (0.3) be fulfilled, and $\text{Im } \rho < -\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$. Then for $c_1 = 1, c_2 = 0$ the

equation (1.3) has the solution $y_1(x, \rho)$ analytic with respect to ρ in $\text{Im } \rho < -\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$ for each fixed $x \in R_-^+$ and admitting the asymptotics

$$\frac{d^j y_1(x, \rho)}{dx^j} = e^{\rho \omega_1 x} [(\rho \omega_1)^j + O(e^{-2\varepsilon_0 x})], \quad j = 0, 1, \text{ as } x \rightarrow \infty. \quad (1.4)$$

Proof. Differentiating the both parts of (1.3) for $c_1 = 1, c_2 = 0$ we obtain:

$$y'(x, \rho) = \rho \omega_1 e^{\rho \omega_1 x} - \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \int_x^{\infty} e^{\rho \omega_1(x-\tau)} + e^{\rho \omega_2(x-\tau)} [p(\tau) y'(\tau, \rho) + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} K(\tau, s, \rho) y'(s, \rho) ds] d\tau \right\}. \quad (1.5)$$

Taking into account the condition (0.2) we obtain

$$y(x, \rho) = \rho \omega_1 e^{\rho \omega_1 x} - \frac{1}{2} \int_x^{\infty} [e^{\rho \omega_1(x-\tau)} + e^{\rho \omega_2(x-\tau)} + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{\rho \omega_1(x-2s+\tau)} + e^{\rho \omega_2(x-\tau)}] \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} K(s, \tau, \rho) y'(\tau, \rho) d\tau. \quad (1.6)$$

Put in equation (1.6)

$$y_1' = \rho\omega_1 e^{\rho\omega_1 x} z(x, \rho)$$

and obtain the equation

$$z(x, \rho) = 1 + Hz \tag{1.7}$$

where

$$H2 = -\int_x^\infty p(\tau) \left\{ \frac{1 - e^{2\rho\omega_1(\tau-x)}}{2\rho\omega_1} + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{e^{2\rho\omega_1(\tau-s)} - e^{2\rho\omega_1(\tau-x)}}{2\rho\omega_1} K^*(s, \tau, \rho) ds \right\} z(\tau, \rho) d\tau.$$

We carry out the proof for the equation (1.7). Write the solution of the equation (1.7) in the form of the Neumann series

$$z(x, \rho) = 1 + H1 + H^2 1 + \dots \tag{1.8}$$

Show that for $x \geq 0$ the series (1.8) converges uniformly for all ρ in the domain $\text{Im } \rho < -\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$.

Indeed, for $\tau > x \geq 0$, $\text{Im } \rho > -\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$ we have $e^{2\rho_2(\tau-x)}$

$$e^{-2\rho_2(\tau-s)} \leq e^{\varepsilon_0(\tau-x)} \text{ and } e^{-\varepsilon_0(x+s)} \leq 1.$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} |H1| &\leq \frac{1}{2|\rho|} \int_x^\infty |p(\tau)| \left\{ 1 + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} [e^{-2\rho_2(\tau+s)} + e^{-2\rho_2(\tau-x)}] |K^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right\} d\tau \leq \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2|\rho|} \int_0^\infty |p(\tau)| e^{\varepsilon_0(\tau-x)} \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |K^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right] d\tau. \end{aligned}$$

For $\tau > x \geq 0$, $\tau - x = t > 0$, $\tau = x + t > 0$.

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} |H1| &\leq \frac{1}{2|\rho|} \int_0^\infty |p(x+t)| e^{\varepsilon_0 t} \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |K^*(s, x+t, \rho)| ds \right] dt \leq \\ &\leq \frac{c}{2|\rho|} \int_0^\infty e^{-2\varepsilon_0(x+t)} e^{\varepsilon_0 t} dt = \frac{cc_1}{\varepsilon_0} e^{-2\varepsilon_0 x}, \end{aligned}$$

where $c_1 = \frac{1}{2|\rho|}$:

$$\begin{aligned} |H^2 1| &\leq \int_x^\infty (1 + p(\tau)) \left\{ \frac{1 - e^{2\rho\omega_1(\tau-x)}}{2\rho} + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{e^{2\rho\omega_1(\tau-x)} + e^{2\rho\omega_1(\tau-x)}}{2\rho} K^*(s, \tau, \rho) ds \right\} |H1| d\tau \leq \\ &\leq \frac{(cc_1)^2}{\varepsilon_0} \int_0^\infty e^{-\varepsilon_0(x+t)} e^{\varepsilon_0 t} e^{-2\varepsilon_0(x+t)} dt = \frac{(cc_1)^2}{2!\varepsilon_0^2} e^{-3\varepsilon_0 x}. \end{aligned}$$

By the induction $|H^n 1| \leq \frac{(cc_1)^n}{n!\varepsilon_0^n} e^{-(n+1)\varepsilon_0 x}$. Therefore, the series (1.7) for $x \geq 0$ is majorized with

a convergent number series and so, it is $\text{sum}z(x, \rho)$ will be analytic with respect to ρ the domain

$\text{Im } \rho > -\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$ for each fixed $x \geq 0$.

Since the sum $\text{sum}z(x, \rho)$ of the series (1.7) in modulus does not exceed the sum of the series

$$1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(cc_1)^n}{n! \varepsilon_0^n} e^{-(n+1)\varepsilon_0 x}$$

This implies the boundedness of $z(x, \rho)$ in $0 \leq x < \infty$, $\text{Im } \rho > -\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$. So, $|z(x, \rho)| \leq A$.

We now estimate the integral summand in (1.7)

$$|H2| \leq A|H1| \leq \frac{Ac_1c_2}{\varepsilon_0} e^{-2\varepsilon_0 x} \rightarrow o(e^{-2\varepsilon_0 x}) \text{ as } x \rightarrow \infty.$$

Then $z(x, \rho) = 1 + o(e^{-2\varepsilon_0 x})$ uniformly with respect to ρ in the domain $x \in R_+^+$ $\text{Im } \rho > -\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$

Assume $z(x, \rho)$ that in $y_1'(x, \rho) = \rho\omega_1 e^{\rho\omega_1 x} z(x, \rho)$, and obtain (1.5) for $j=1$ and $j=0$, $y_1(x, \rho) = e^{-\rho\omega_1 x} (1 + o(e^{-2\varepsilon_0 x}))$.

Behaving in the same way, we prove that there exists a solution $y_2(x, \rho)$ of integro-differential equation

(1.1) analytic with respect to p in the domain $\text{Im } \rho > -\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$ for each fixed from the interval $R_+^+ = (0, \infty)$

and admitting the asymptotics

$$\frac{d^j y_2(x, \rho)}{dx^j} = e^{\rho\omega_2 x} [(\rho\omega_2)^j + o(e^{-2\varepsilon_0 x})] \quad j = 0,1, \text{ as } x \rightarrow +\infty \tag{1.8}$$

Obviously, $y_1(x, \rho), y_2(x, \rho)$ satisfy the equation (1.6) for $x \geq 0$ and it is easy to verify directly that they will be the solutions of the integro-differential equation (1.1) as well for $x \geq 0$

Since the obtained solutions are linearly independent, using the uniqueness of the solution of the Cauchy problem and for $x \leq 0$ as the solution of the integro-differential equation (1.1).

So we proved Theorem 1.1

Applying the method for proving theorem 1.1. we can prove the following statement:

Theorem 1.2. Let the condition (0.3) be fulfilled, and $\text{Im } \rho < \frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$. Then the integro-differential equation

(1.1) has two linearly independent solutions $y_k(x, \rho)$, analytic with respect to ρ in $\text{Im } \rho < \frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$ for each

fixed $x \in R_+^+$ and admitting the asymptotics

$$\frac{d^j y_k(x, \rho)}{dx^j} = e^{\rho\omega_k x} [(\rho\omega_k)^j + o(e^{2\varepsilon_0 x})] \text{ as } x \rightarrow -\infty. \tag{1.9}$$

To prove this we need to consider the integral equation

$$y(x, \rho) = \sum_{i=1}^2 c_i e^{\rho\omega_i x} - \frac{\omega_1}{2\rho} \int_{-\infty}^x p(\tau) \left\{ e^{\rho\omega_1(x-\tau)} - e^{\rho\omega_2(x-\tau)} + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} [e^{\rho\omega_1(x-\tau)} - e^{\rho\omega_1(x-2s+\tau)}] K^*(s, \tau, \rho) ds \right\} y'(\tau) d\tau.$$

Theorem 1.3. Let the condition (0.3) be fulfilled. Then for $\text{Im } \rho > -\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$ and as $|\rho| \rightarrow \infty$

$$\frac{d^j y_k(x, \rho)}{dx^j} = e^{\rho\omega_k x} \left[(\rho\omega_k)^j + o\left(\frac{1}{\rho}\right) \right], \quad j = 0,1, \quad k = 1,2. \tag{1.10}$$

uniformly with respect to x

Proof. Let us consider again the equation (1.6).

Let $|z_k(x, \rho)| \leq A$ for $x \in R_-^+$, $\text{Im } \rho > -\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$.

Then

$$|Hz_k| \leq A|H1| \leq \frac{Ac}{|\rho|\varepsilon_0} e^{-2\varepsilon_0 x} \rightarrow o\left(\frac{1}{\rho}\right) \text{ as } |\rho| \rightarrow \infty$$

Thus,

$$z_k(x, \rho) = 1 + \left(\frac{1}{\rho}\right) \text{ uniformly with respect to } x.$$

Assume $z_k(x, \rho)$ in $y_k'(x, \rho) = \rho\omega_k e^{\rho\omega_k x} z_k(x, \rho)$ and obtain (1.10) for $j = 1$. In a similar way we can obtain (1.10) for $j = 0$.

Now, let the following condition be fulfilled:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |p(x)| \left\| \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} K^*(s, x, \rho) ds \right] \right\| dx < B < \infty. \quad (1.11)$$

where B is independent of ρ .

Theorem 1.4. Let the condition (1.11) be fulfilled, and $|\rho| \geq \tau > 0$, $\text{Im } \rho > 0$, where $r > B$.

Then the integro-differential equation (1.1) in the half-plane $\text{Im } \rho > 0$ has two linearly independent solutions $y_k(x, \rho)$, $k = 1, 2$, analytic in this domain with respect to ρ for each fixed $x \in R_-^+$ and admitting the asymptotics

$$\frac{d^j y_k(x, \rho)}{dx^j} = e^{\rho\omega_k x} \left[(\rho\omega_k)^j + o(1) \right], \quad j = 0, 1, \quad k = 1, 2, \text{ as } |x| \rightarrow \infty \quad (1.12)$$

References

1. Naimark M.A. Linear differential operators Nauka, Moscow, 1969, 24-150.
2. Naimark M.A. Studying spectrum and expansion in eigen functions of a second order not self-adjoint differential operator on a semi-axis. Trudy Moskovskogo Matematicheskogo Obshestva, №3, 1954, p.181-270.
3. Naimark M.A. Spectral analysis of not self-adjoint operators. UMN, 11, 6(72), 1956, p.183-202.
4. Sansone J. Ordinary differential equations. I-II, 1953.
5. Kato T. theory of perturbations of linear operators M.Mir, 1972.
6. B.B. Korotkov Integral operators. Nauka, Siberian branch. Novosibirsk, 1983, p.58-73.
7. Alammadov M.S. On a spectrum of a fourth order linear integro-differential operator. Doklady AN SSSR, v.29, №3, 1988, p.525-529.
8. Alammadov M.S. Asymptotic formulas of the solutions of linear integro differential equation $L(y) = \lambda g$. Sciences of Europe Praha, Czech Republic no.113(2023), p.71-77.